

Enhancing outcrossing potential in hybrid rice

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In spite of a successful hybrid rice research program in India, the nonavailability of good-quality seed of CMS-based hybrids, released in the recent past to farmers at a reasonable price, remains a big challenge (Rai 2004). Among other factors, the inherent low variability of suitable floral traits, which influence outcrossing, in parental lines of the respective hybrids is itself a key factor responsible for the low percentage of seed set (Liang et al 1991, Virmani and Athwal 1974, Yadav et al 1998). Keeping these in view along with the mode of action of some homoeopathic medicine on human reproductive systems, a number of these resources were tried to explore their usefulness in enhancing outcrossing of parental lines of hybrid rice. Among them, Pulsatilla, Agnus Cast, and Acid Phos were found worth investigating (Yadav and Srivastava 2003).

This study used a set of IR58025A/NDR3026-3-1 planted at 2 males:10 females in a plot size of 4 × 5 m² in a randomized block design with four replications during the 2001, 2002, and 2003 wet seasons at the Crop Research Station in Masodha (26.47°N, 82.12°E, 113 m altitude). Soil at the experimental field was silty loam, with 0.38% organic carbon, 138.50 kg available N ha⁻¹, 18.35 kg available P ha⁻¹, 172 kg available K ha⁻¹, and pH 7.5. The spacing adopted was 30 cm between male rows, 25 cm between male and female rows, 20 cm between female rows, and 15 cm between hills. A 21-d-old single seedling

was transplanted in each hill perpendicular to the wind direction. The recommended package of practices was followed to raise the crop (Yadav and Srivastava 2003). Pulsatilla 200 (SBL) at a concentration of 1:100 (chemical and water) was applied before heading, whereas GA₃ (60 g ha⁻¹) was applied at 5–10% panicle emergence on female lines. Agnus Cast 200 (SBL) and Acid Phos 200 (SBL) were also applied at the same concentration (1:100) on alternate days prior to panicle

emergence on male lines. Spraying was done using a knapsack sprayer in the evening during clear weather. Flag leaf clipping and supplementary pollination were also done. Fifteen flowers per plant were randomly marked to record relevant observations (Table 1) (Virmani and Athwal 1974), whereas seed yield was obtained on a per-plot basis. ISTA rules (ISTA 1999) were followed in recording some important seed quality parameters (Table 2).

Table 1. Pollination characteristics of hybrid rice as affected by various treatments using the same homoeopathic medicine (pooled data over 3 y).

Treatment	Female parent (IR58025A)			
	Duration of floret opening (min)	Blooming duration of panicle (d)	Angle of floret opening (°)	Stigma exertion (%)
GA ₃ at 60 g ha ⁻¹	196.12	5.41	50.83	68.61
Pulsatilla 200	256.00	6.07	63.52	78.53
GA ₃ + Pulsatilla 200	215.10	6.33	65.21	80.10
Control	151.12	5.11	40.23	42.81
LSD 5%	50.79	0.83	5.80	6.90

Treatment	Male parent (NDR3026-3-1)		
	Blooming duration of panicle (d)	Residual pollen (%)	Duration of pollen viability (min)
Agnus Cast 200 + Acid Phos 200	7.4 ^{ab}	87.34 ^{ab}	12.22 ^{ab}
Control	6.0	65.00	7.81

^a*P = 0.05, ^b**P = 0.01 (t test).

Table 2. Seed yield, seed quality parameters, and longevity of NDRH2 as affected by some treatments (pooled data over 3 y).

Treatment	Seed set (%)	Seed yield (t ha ⁻¹)	1,000-seed wt (g)	Seed discoloration (%)	Opened glume (%)	Germination (%) ^a	Vigor index ^a
GA ₃ at 60 g ha ⁻¹	40.91	1.52	18.03	12.45	28.16	78.29	1,087.13
Pulsatilla 200	35.50	1.25	18.20	8.25	1.20	89.13	1,351.09
GA ₃ + Pulsatilla 200	54.27	2.19	18.27	5.19	1.40	87.91	1,296.42
Control	15.18	0.53	18.25	14.10	20.93	79.51	1,125.52
LSD 5%	5.35	0.29	ns	6.27	7.09	2.19	26.90

^aSix-month storage after harvest under ambient conditions. ^bns = nonsignificant.

Pulsatilla 200 was found most effective in improving significantly the duration of floret opening, blooming duration of panicle, angle of floret opening, and stigma exertion in comparison with the control and GA₃ application. The application of Agnus Cast 200 and Acid Phos 200 increased significantly the blooming duration of panicles, the percentage of residual pollen, and the duration of pollen viability (Table 1). These enhanced outcrossing characteristics led to an increase in seed set (54.27), seed yield (2.2 t ha⁻¹), and various quality parameters and longevity, even in comparison with hybrid seed obtained after

GA₃ application (60 g ha⁻¹), a common treatment in hybrid rice seed production (Table 2). The results show that such eco-friendly treatments can be successfully used in the production of precious hybrid seed in rice particularly and could also be tried for some other hybrid cultures.

References

ISTA (International Seed Testing Association). 1999. International rules for seed testing. *Seed Sci. Technol.* 27:285-297.

Liang KJ, Yang RC, Wang NY, Chen QH. 1991. Comparison of characters of CMS lines and their maintainers in indica hybrid rice. *J. Fujian Agric. Coll.* 20(4):367-373.

Rai M. 2004. Evolution of seed research and development in India. In: Sovn. National Conference on Seed: a global perspective. 26-28 Mar, Delhi, India. p 4-5.

Virmani SS, Athwal DS. 1974. Inheritance of floral characteristics influencing outcrossing in rice. *Crop Sci.* 14:350-353.

Yadav RDS, Srivastava JP. 2003. Evaluation and utilization of homeopathic resources for enhancing outcrossing in parental lines of hybrid rice. In: Proceedings of the 6th Agricultural Science Congress, 13-15 Feb, Bhopal, India. p 79.

Yadav RDS, Singh PV, Srivastava JP. 1998. Research developments and challenges in hybrid rice seed production for the 21st century. *Seed Technol. News* 28(4):16.

